

Conference Abstract

The Distribution of the Belica *Leucaspilus delineatus* and the Crucian Carp *Carassius carassius* in Hungary over the Past Fifty Years and the Threats to the Persistence of Their Populations

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Abstract

In the Carpathian Basin, large-scale water regulation projects in the 18th century – primarily the drainage of extensive marshlands – led to a substantial reduction of wetland habitats, which in turn caused significant declines in the populations of marsh-dwelling fish species. The Belica *Leucaspilus delineatus* is also among these rare marsh fauna elements, for which distribution data are still scarce. In Hungary, the Belica is currently classified as “protected”. Its most typical habitats are marshes and wetland areas where it co-occurs with other threatened marsh fish species such as Tench *Tinca tinca*, Crucian Carp *Carassius carassius*, Weatherfish *Misgurnus fossilis*, and Mudminnow *Umbra krameri*. Additionally, populations have been recorded from mid-mountain streams, where it coexists with species such as Chub *Squalius cephalus*, Danube Gudgeon *Gobio obtusirostris*, and Stone Loach *Barbatula barbatula*. In several cases, it has also been found in small lowland drainage channels, degraded habitats, and in small pits or oxbows within the floodplains of larger rivers. The Crucian Carp *Carassius carassius*,

became the second most endangered fish species in Romania by the 1990s, after the *Romanichthys valsanicola*. Unfortunately, the situation in Hungary is similar. The invasive Prussian Carp *Carassius gibelio* is now considered the most common fish species in Hungary, and has spread even into isolated marsh habitats where the Crucian Carp is gradually being displaced. The Crucian Carp has disappeared from many sites, especially oxbows, due to fishing exploitation and illegal introductions of the Prussian Carp. Unfortunately, the Crucian Carp does not currently enjoy legal nature conservation protection in Hungary, although its capture is prohibited year-round. Field surveys were conducted primarily using low-voltage battery-powered electrofishing gear. Data collection was often carried out under challenging field conditions, caused partly by dense submerged and emergent aquatic vegetation, and partly by deep soft sediments. At most survey sites, photographic documentation of the habitat was taken, the most common water quality parameters were measured (pH, dissolved oxygen content, conductivity, water temperature), and the number of individuals of captured species was recorded using a digital voice recorder. In this presentation, we aim to provide an overview of the distribution of these two endangered marsh fish species in Hungary over the past 50 years and to identify the main threats to the persistence of their populations.

Keywords

ecology, endangered species, habitat loss, electrofishing, faunistic research

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.